

Synthesising Knocking Sound Effects Using Conditional WaveGAN

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we explore the synthesis of sound effects using conditional generative adversarial networks (cGANs). We commissioned Foley artist Ulf Olausson to record a dataset of knocking sound effects with different emotions and trained a cGAN on it. We analysed the resulting synthesised sound effects by comparing their temporal acoustic features to the original dataset and by performing an online listening test. Results show that the acoustic features of the synthesised sounds are similar to those of the recorded dataset. Additionally, the listening test results show that the synthesised sounds can be identified by people with experience in sound design, but the model is not far from fooling non-experts. Moreover, on average most emotions can be recognised correctly in both recorded and synthesised sounds. Given that the temporal acoustic features of the two datasets are highly similar, we hypothesise that they strongly contribute to the perception of the intended emotions in the recorded and synthesised knocking sounds.

1. INTRODUCTION

Video games and interactive media are mostly sound designed using pre-recorded samples. In order to avoid repetition when a user repeats an action, several sound effects are used for the same action. This creates an overhead in terms of asset management and implementation time. As opposed to pre-recorded samples, procedural audio, in the context of video games, refers to the use of audio synthesis during gameplay [1]. Among its benefits, sound synthesis can generate infinite variations of sound effects, adapting the sound to the game parameters.

Knocking sound effects are a key element in storytelling: they are often used as a transition element. For example, in films a knocking action can express the emotions of the person knocking at the door, as well as create expectations in the audience about the possible reactions of a character hearing the knock. Knocking sound effects are an interesting subject of study for sound synthesis because they have

a frequency-domain (the individual knock synthesis) component as well as a highly articulated time-domain (how the knocks are arranged in time) component.

Knocking sound effects are composed from one or more impact-sounds against a surface. While impact-sounds are often synthesised using modal synthesis [2], novel architectures in machine learning, and more specifically deep learning, open the possibility of synthesising sounds using alternative methods. The technique of synthesising audio using deep learning is often called neural audio synthesis [3]. In the context of deep learning, generative models are those that learn the statistical latent space from a dataset and create new data by sampling from it [4]. In other words, generative models can generate new unseen data by learning from a training dataset, and the new generated data will have similar characteristics to those of the training dataset.

GANs [5] have two components: a discriminator (also called critic when using Wasserstein [6] or WGAN-GP [7]) and a generator. The discriminator (or critic) is a neural network with the goal of predicting whether a sample is real or fake. The generator is also a neural network that aims to fool the discriminator by starting from random values (usually noise sampled from a Gaussian distribution) and updating its parameters until it is able to create an output good enough to fool the discriminator. The generation from GANs is not conditioned. cGANs [8] are an extension to GANs that allow to introduce more data (such as a class label) to further condition the generation of the model. For instance, a GAN generator trained on a corpus of footstep sound effects on different surfaces will output a footstep each time on a different random surface. However, if a surface label is added to the model, the generator can be controlled to output a sound on a particular surface.

GANs have been used for tasks such as computer vision to generate ultra-realistic human face images [9] or procedural content generation to generate coloured 3D meshes [10]. Regarding the use of GANs for audio synthesis, different architectures have been proposed, such as WaveGAN [11] and GANSynth. [12]. WaveGAN learns directly from raw audio data (sound files) and produces raw audio data. WaveGAN is based on DCGAN (deep convolutional GAN) [13], but using one-dimensional convolutions instead of two-dimensional convolutions in order to process the raw audio data (as opposed to images). GANSynth uses an architecture similar to progressive GAN [14] and different audio representations (such as spectrograms

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and mel-spectrograms) instead of raw audio. GANSynth reported better scores than WaveGAN on human perceptual evaluation for musical notes with pitch conditioning. While GANs do not synthesise audio in real-time, the generation time is remarkably fast (especially for batches of sounds thanks to parallelisation).

We decided to use the WaveGAN architecture given its simplicity and the good perceptual results it produces when synthesising drum samples in a virtual environment [15], which can represent a close scenario to the synthesis of knocking sound effects in a video game. Pilot studies exist aimed to condition the generation of WaveGAN applied to speech synthesis [16], although authors found the generated audio files too noisy. Our objective is to use the conditional WaveGAN architecture to explore the synthesis of knocking sounds effects with different emotional intentions and analyse the results in terms of synthesis plausibility, acoustic features and emotion portrayed.

2. KNOCKING SOUND EFFECTS DATASET

In order to train the cGAN to synthesise the sound effects, we asked the professional Foley artist Ulf Olausson to record a dataset of knocking sound effects at the FoleyWorks studios in Stockholm¹. Inspired by previous work on knocking sounds [17], we chose five basic emotions [18] to be portrayed in the dataset: anger, fear, happiness, neutral and sadness. We gave the Foley artist the following scenarios to perform the knocking actions:

- Anger: telling a flatmate for the 4th time to turn down the very loud music.
- Fear: alerting a neighbour of a possible risk.
- Happiness: telling a flatmate that they won a prize.
- Neutral: parcel delivery.
- Sadness: telling a friend that someone passed away.

We also asked the Foley artist to perform diverse interpretations of the provided scenarios in order to produce a wider variety of sounds. The dataset was recorded with a Rode NT1 microphone, performing the knocks to a closed door (Figure 1).

We recorded a total of 600 knocking actions (120 actions per category). An action is a sequence of individual knocks. We discarded 20 actions per category to filter out unwanted noise. The final 500 audio files were trimmed so each file started on the first knock onset and finished on the last knock decay. The dataset can be accessed from the online repository [19].

2.1 Acoustic Analysis

Research in music performance and speech [20] has demonstrated that sound performed with different intended emotions present emotion-specific acoustic patterns. Therefore in order to understand the variations of the knocking patterns for different emotions, and to compare the original

¹ <http://foleyworks.se/>

Figure 1: Microphone placement during the recording.

dataset to the synthesised sounds, we extracted different acoustic features from the dataset. The different features used for the analysis are the following:

Figure 2: Example of the root-mean-square energy feature. The X axis represents knocking action duration in seconds. The Y axis represents the RMSE of the individual knocks. The individual knock positions in the action are represented by the black dots. The slope of the fitted line (in red) is negative, therefore the action has a decrescendo energy pattern.

- *Action duration*: Length of the knocking action. The knocking action length is the time passed from the first knock onset to the last knock decay.
- *Number of knocks per action*: The number of knocks were retrieved by counting the number of onsets detected in each audio file.
- *Knocking rate*: The knocking rate was retrieved by dividing the number of knocks in an action by the total time of the action. This feature is applied only to actions with 2 or more knocks.
- *Knocking regularity*: The knocking regularity measures how regular the knocks are in an action. Actions where the knocks are performed on a steady pace will show a higher regularity. To extract this

feature, we calculated the inter-onset interval (IOI) of each action and computed the coefficient of variation (the standard deviation divided by the mean). Irregular actions will have higher coefficient of variation. This feature is applied only to actions with more than 2 knocks.

- *Root-mean-square energy (RMSE) slope*: This retrieves the energy pattern (crescendo or decrescendo) of an action. We calculated the root-mean-square energy of each individual knock and applied a linear regression to each action. The slope of the fitted line determines the energy crescendo (positive values) or decrescendo (negative values) of the action. An example of this feature applied to an individual action can be seen in Figure 2. This feature is applied only to actions with 2 or more knocks.

These features were utilised by the authors in a parallel study on the emotion perception in knocking actions of naive performers [21] in order to allow future comparison of the results.

3. METHOD

3.1 Sound Synthesis

As mentioned, we used a conditional WaveGAN architecture to synthesise the audio. We conditioned the architecture to accept the input label corresponding to the different knocking action’s emotion. As the longest knocking action in the recorded dataset is 2.85 seconds, we used the largest version of the architecture that allows the processing of 65536 samples. We used a sampling rate of 22050Hz to fit all knocking actions in the architecture (the longest action has 62843 samples using the 22050Hz sampling rate).

We ran a series of pilot experiments with different hyper-parameters. While we used most of the hyper-parameters proposed in the WaveGAN paper, we found phase shuffle worsened the output of our model, therefore we discarded it. We judged the performance of the model subjectively by synthesising a knocking sound effect per different emotion every 200 batches of the training loop. After the pilot experiments, we set the critic loops to 5, the learning rate (for both the critic and the generator) to 0.0002 and the batch size to 128. We used WGAN-GP, batch normalisation, Adam optimiser and no phase shuffle. We trained the model on a NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU for 72 hours.

We synthesised a total of 500 sounds (100 sounds per emotion) to compare the synthesised sounds to the original dataset. We did not favour the best sounding synthesised samples: they are the raw output from the model. The synthesis of the 500 sound effects took a total of 30 seconds on a NVIDIA GTX 1060 GPU.

Our Keras implementation of the conditional WaveGAN architecture is available in the online repository².

² Code: https://github.com/adrianbarahona/conditional_wavegan_knocking_sounds

3.2 Perceptual Evaluation

To understand how the sounds are perceived, we made an online listening test. The listening test had two objectives: to determine whether or not the synthesised sound effects are distinguishable from the recorded sounds in the dataset, and to learn whether or not the intended emotion of the knocking action (recorded or synthesised) could be identified.

To learn how the synthesised sounds are perceptually perceived compared to the recorded dataset, we planned our listening test using the guidelines of the RS (real and synthetic) listening test [22]. The objective of the test is to determine how distinguishable the synthesised sounds are from the recorded ones. The test was done online. Participants were asked to use headphones. Overall the listening conditions were considered to be similar to those of a person playing a video game using their own equipment. As a control mechanism, we introduced an ‘acid’ (a clearly synthesised sound) sample as suggested by the RS listening test guidelines.

The metrics used from the RS listening test were the discriminator factor d and the F -measure. The discriminator factor d is defined as:

$$d = \frac{P_{CS} - P_{FP} + 1}{2} \quad (1)$$

Where P_{CS} are the percentage of the samples correctly labeled as synthetic and P_{FP} are the percentage of the recorded samples labeled as synthetic (false positives). The F -measure is defined as:

$$F - measure = \frac{(\beta^2 + 1) \times Precision \times Recall}{\beta^2 \times Precision + Recall} \quad (2)$$

Where precision and recall are defined as:

$$Precision = \frac{P_{CS}}{P_{CS} + P_{FP}} \quad (3)$$

$$Recall = \frac{P_{CS}}{P_{CS} + P_{FN}} \quad (4)$$

With P_{FN} being the percentage of synthetic sounds labeled as recorded and $\beta = 1$.

In terms of the interpretation of d and the F -measure, values below 0.5 are no different from random guessing, and values close to 1.0 show the recorded and synthetic sounds are clearly distinguishable from each other. Values below 0.75 show there is no clear distinction between recorded and synthetic sounds.

To measure how the emotions are perceived in both the recorded dataset and in the synthesised sounds, we performed a Chi-square test on the emotion labeling by the participants.

We used the online platform Qualtrics³ to carry out the listening test. Each participant was presented with a total of 51 sounds. 25 sounds were recorded (5 per emotion), 25 sounds were synthesised (5 per emotion) and 1 sound was the acid test. The selection of sounds, and the order

³ <https://www.qualtrics.com>

in which they were presented, were randomised for each participant. The sounds were presented in their original format: 48000Hz/16bit WAV for the recorded sounds and 22050Hz/32bit WAV for the synthesised sounds. Again, the model uses a sampling rate of 22050Hz to fit all the knocking actions in the architecture. While the difference in sampling rates between the recorded and synthesised sounds could affect the perceptual evaluation, we decided to maintain the original sampling rates given that it better represents the performance of the model against pre-recorded sounds.

The participants were asked to label each sound as ‘recorded’ or ‘synthesised’ and to choose the emotion each sound represents the most (Figure 3). Participants were also asked their level of expertise in sound design, ranked from 1 (no expertise) to 5 (professional).

Figure 3: Online test interface.

4. RESULTS

Sound examples of both the recorded dataset and the synthesised sounds can be found in the webpage of the project⁴.

4.1 Comparison of Recorded and Synthesised Sounds Acoustic Features

The acoustic analysis of both the recorded dataset and the synthesised sounds is shown in Figure 4. When comparing the analysed features for both the recorded dataset (left column, Figures 4a, 4c, 4e, 4g and 4i) and the synthesised sounds (right column, Figures 4b, 4d, 4f, 4h and 4j), it is clear that the synthesised sounds retain the features from the recorded dataset. While their distributions are not identical, synthesised sounds follow the recorded dataset trend in all the analysed features.

4.2 Listening Test Results

A total of 22 participants (17 males, 5 females) with ages from 18 to 58 took the online listening test. 14 of the participants reported no experience in sound design, 2 participants a level of 2 out of 5, 3 participants a level of 3 out of 5, 2 participants a level of 4 out of 5 and 1 participant a level of 5 out of 5.

One participant failed to label the ‘acid’ sample correctly and therefore was removed from the evaluation completely.

⁴ Sound examples: https://www.adrianbarahonarios.com/conditional_wavegan_knocking_sounds/

Another participant did not label the emotion of one sound file and therefore was removed from the evaluation of the emotion labeling.

The average values of the RS listening test can be seen in Table 1. The raw percentage of participants who correctly labeled the recorded and synthesised sounds can be seen in Table 2. A visualisation of the average RS test results with the individual scores separated by the level of the participants level of expertise in sound design is shown in Figure 5. While the RS listening test results are on average below the 0.75 threshold, synthesised samples can definitely be identified by persons with medium to high experience in sound design. However, some people with low experience in sound design are unable to detect them.

The raw percentage of the participant emotion labeling for the recorded dataset is shown in Table 3. We performed a Chi-Square Test with $\chi^2(16, N = 500) = 564.341, p = .000 < .05$ (columns compared with a z-test and p values adjusted with Bonferroni method). Results show that anger, happiness, neutral and sadness are statistically different from others. Anger and fear are not statistically different from each other, but they are statistically different from the other emotions. This indicates that fear is confused with anger. For the synthesised sounds, the raw percentage of the participant emotion labeling is shown in Table 4. We performed a Chi-Square Test with $\chi^2(16, N = 500) = 376.371, p = .000 < .05$ (columns compared with a z-test and p values adjusted with Bonferroni method). Identically to the recorded emotion labeling results, the Chi-Square Test shows that anger, happiness, neutral and sadness are statistically different from others and that anger and fear are not statistically different from each other, but they are statistically different from the other emotions.

5. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper explored the synthesis of knocking sound effects with emotional intention using a conditional WaveGAN architecture. We analysed the results in terms of synthesis plausibility (how distinguishable are the synthesised samples from the original dataset), acoustic features and emotion.

Results show that the model is close to be able to synthesise samples that would be indistinguishable from their recorded counterparts for persons without experience in sound design. However, synthesised sounds are easily identifiable for people with experience in sound design. To explore how to improve the model perceptually, we plan, in future work, to use the GANSynth architecture to compare it with the conditional WaveGAN architecture on the synthesis of knocking sound effects. GANSynth already reported better perceptual results on musical notes with pitch conditioning, and might produce better results in the synthesis of sound effects too.

In terms of the intended (and labelled) emotions, results show that, on average, most emotions can be recognised correctly in both the recorded and the synthesised sound groups. In both groups fear is confused with anger. This means that, despite the fact that recorded and synthesised sounds can be distinguished, the emotional characteristics

(a) Action duration per emotion (recorded dataset).

(b) Action duration per emotion (synthesised sounds).

(c) Number of knocks in each action (recorded dataset).

(d) Number of knocks in each action (synthesised sounds).

(e) Knocking rate per action per emotion (recorded dataset).

(f) Knocking rate per action per emotion (synthesised sounds).

(g) Knocking regularity per action per emotion (recorded dataset).

(h) Knocking regularity per action per emotion (synthesised sounds).

(i) Slope of the actions RMS energy (recorded dataset).

(j) Slope of the actions RMS energy (synthesised sounds).

Figure 4: Recorded dataset and synthesised sounds analysis results. The left column (Figures 4a, 4c, 4e, 4g and 4i) shows the results for the recorded dataset. The right column (Figures 4b, 4d, 4f, 4h and 4j) shows the results for the synthesised sounds. In Figures 4g and 4h higher values indicate less regularity.

Avg d	σ	σ^2	Avg F-measure	σ	σ^2
0.63	0.31	0.09	0.67	0.24	0.06

 Table 1: RS listening test d and F-measure values across all participants.

Emotion	Correctly labeled as recorded	Emotion	Correctly labeled as synthesised
[Recorded] Anger	73.3%	[Synthesised] Anger	60.9%
[Recorded] Fear	72.4%	[Synthesised] Fear	60.0%
[Recorded] Happiness	80.9%	[Synthesised] Happiness	63.4%
[Recorded] Neutral	68.6%	[Synthesised] Neutral	65.7%
[Recorded] Sadness	60.9%	[Synthesised] Sadness	65.7%

Table 2: Real and synthesised labeling by the participants (raw results).

	[Perceived] Anger	[Perceived] Fear	[Perceived] Happiness	[Perceived] Neutral	[Perceived] Sadness
[Intended] Anger	68.0%	12.0%	10.0%	10.0%	0.0%
[Intended] Fear	60.0%	28.0%	5.0%	5.0%	2.0%
[Intended] Happiness	4.0%	2.0%	64.0%	27.0%	3.0%
[Intended] Neutral	5.0%	6.0%	15.0%	63.0%	11.0%
[Intended] Sadness	2.0%	10.0%	2.0%	29.0%	57.0%

Table 3: Recorded dataset intended and perceived emotion labeling by the participants.

	[Perceived] Anger	[Perceived] Fear	[Perceived] Happiness	[Perceived] Neutral	[Perceived] Sadness
[Intended] Anger	47.0%	19.0%	8.0%	18.0%	8.0%
[Intended] Fear	40.0%	44.0%	9.0%	7.0%	0.0%
[Intended] Happiness	1.0%	12.0%	44.0%	37.0%	6.0%
[Intended] Neutral	6.0%	6.0%	17.0%	62.0%	9.0%
[Intended] Sadness	0.0%	16.0%	3.0%	34.0%	47.0%

Table 4: Synthesised sounds intended and perceived emotion labeling by the participants.

 Figure 5: d and F-measure values across all participants and emotions (box plot) and individual scores for each participant (swarm plot). The level of expertise in sound design of each participant is represented by the dot color.

of the recorded dataset are present in the synthesised sounds.

Since the acoustic features of the synthesised dataset are very similar to those of the recorded dataset, we hypothesise that they strongly contribute to the perception of emotions, and that they are sufficiently well modelled in the synthesised dataset to allow listeners to perceive the in-

tended emotions as well as they are in the recorded dataset.

Additionally, the acoustic features distribution is not exactly the same in the two datasets. This is actually desirable considering that the aim is to generate new data and not to re-synthesise data that was already in the training dataset. However, diversity of new generated data is challenging when using generative methods, especially for audio [23]. In the case of the synthesised knocking sound effects, upon subjective qualitative evaluation, some can be traced back to the original recorded sound on which they were trained from. In future work we plan to tackle this problem.

Regarding the control over the synthesised samples, the model is capable of synthesise knocking sound effects with emotional conditioning. We plan to work on further conditioning the generation of the sounds with other features (such as the features used for the analysis).

In terms of applications, this approach could be used in video games and post-production. While the sound synthesis using GANs is not done in real-time (GANs synthesise one or several sounds at a time, not sample by sample), the sound generation can be fast enough to be used in a real-time scenario without perceived latency [15].

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